

Kinetics of Oxidation of Hydroxyl Ion by Potassium Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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The kinetics of the oxidation of hydroxyl ion in solution by potassium hexacyanoferrate(III), $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ with an applied voltage potential of 0.45 V have been studied and reported in this paper. The effects of hexacyanoferrate ion concentration, pH, and applied voltage at room temperature on the evolution of oxygen are investigated and a probable mechanism for the oxidation reaction is suggested.

It is reported in the literature^{1,2} that potassium hydroxide reacts with potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) in solution, evolving oxygen according to equation (1).

The same reaction, however, does not take place when dilute solutions of potassium hydroxide and potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) solutions are mixed. Moreover, hexacyanoferrate(III) solutions are quite stable in alkaline medium, since thermodynamically the reaction is endothermic with an oxidation potential of 0.46 eV according to the equations

or

It is, however, observed that oxygen evolution does take place when a pellet of potassium hydroxide is added to a solution of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) (~0.1M). This suggests that a localised concentration of hydroxyl ions is essential for the evolution of oxygen in the above system. A potential is applied to simulate the localised concentration at the anode for oxygen evolution. The present paper is concerned with the effect of initial concentration of the reactants, temperature, and external potential on the evolution of oxygen in the above system.

Experimental

Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) and potassium hydroxide used in the experiments were of AnalaR grade. The solutions used were made from distilled water.

A three-necked flask (250 ml) with two platinum electrodes fused at the bottom was used as a cell for carrying out the experiment as shown in Fig. 1. Through one of the necks was connected a burette

closed with a rubber septum for collecting the evolved oxygen, while through the second, a combined electrode for measuring pH of the solution was housed.

Fig. 1. Experimental set up (reaction cell).

The pH of the solution was monitored at 30° using a combined electrode digital Global model no. DPH 500 pH meter after disconnecting the cell. The oxygen gas was identified using a Shimadzu model-5A gas chromatograph with molecular sieve 5A column and helium as carrier gas. DC potential

was applied using Aplab Regulated Power Supply Unit Type LVA 65/5.

Equal quantities of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) and potassium hydroxide solutions at different concentrations were mixed in the above reaction cell. A known potential was applied between the two platinum electrodes. The pH of the solution, the amount of oxygen evolved, and the concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) were measured at different intervals of time. The hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration was estimated iodometrically⁸.

The experiments were carried out at different temperatures, viz. 27, 35, 45 and 55°. The initial concentrations of hexacyanoferrate(III) used in the experiments were in the range 0.02 to 0.5 M. The variation of pH considered in the experiment was from 9 to 13.7 (Fig. 3), while the applied potential was varied from 0.2 to 1.2 V.

Results and Discussion

Variation of oxygen evolution rate with initial concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III): The data on the rate of oxygen evolution at constant potentials of 0.6 and 0.45 V and pH of 13.1 at 27°, varying the initial concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) from 0.05 to 0.4 M, are exhibited in Fig. 2. It is observed that under these conditions, the rate of oxygen evolution increases linearly with the initial concentration of hexacyanoferrate(III) according to the equation (5).

$$\frac{d[O_2]}{dt} = K_8 [Fe(CN)_6]^{3-} \quad (5)$$

The value of K_8 (Fig. 2) is found to be approximately 0.24 ml/(h M) for 0.6 V and 0.08 ml/(h M) for 0.45 V.

Variation of oxygen evolution rate with pH: The variation of oxygen evolution with pH at constant hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration (0.5 M) at 27° and at an applied potential of 0.48 V is described in Fig. 3. As can be easily noted from the figure, the logarithm of the rate of oxygen evolution increases approximately linearly with pH having a slope of 1.4. In other words,

$$\log \frac{d[O_2]}{dt} = 1.4 \text{ pH} + K_4 \quad (6)$$

Substituting for pH and simplifying further, we obtain

$$\frac{d[O_2]}{dt} = K_8 [OH]^{1.4} \quad (7)$$

This indicates that the rate of oxygen evolution is dependent on hydroxyl ion concentration but oxygen is directly evolved in a single step. Probably first an electron transfer reaction takes place giving hydroxyl radical which subsequently reacts to give oxygen according to equations (8) and (9).

Variation of oxygen evolution rate with temperature: Table 1 presents the variation of the rate of oxygen evolution with temperature at constant potential 0.91 V and pH 13.35 with an initial con-

Fig. 2. Variation of the rate of oxygen evolution with the initial hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration at constant temperature and applied voltage.

Fig. 3 Variation of oxygen evolution with pH at constant hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration.

centration of hexacyanoferrate(III) 0.25 M. Table 1 reveals that the rate of evolution of oxygen decreases with increase of temperature. This decrease is possibly attributable to the fact that the organised layer of the ions is disturbed by an increase in the temperature.

TABLE 1 - VARIATION OF RATE OF OXYGEN EVOLUTION WITH TEMPERATURE

Temperature °C	Rate of oxygen evolution $\times 10^{-8}$ mole sec $^{-1}$
35	0.87
45	0.55
55	0.22

Variation of oxygen evolution rate with applied potential: Table 2 presents the trends in the variation of oxygen evolution rate with applied potential at constant pH, initial hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration and temperature. The Table 2 reveals that an increase in the applied voltage or the initial concentration is accompanied by an increase in the rate of oxygen evolution.

TABLE 2 - VARIATION OF OXYGEN EVOLUTION RATE WITH APPLIED POTENTIAL AND INITIAL HEXACYANOFERRATE CONCENTRATION

Initial concentration M	Voltage V	Rate of oxygen evolution $\times 10^8$ ml h $^{-1}$
0.05	0.45	4.5
0.05	0.6	8.3
0.1	0.45	9.5
0.1	0.6	27.7

Remarks on nature of oxygen evolution reaction: It also appears from the oxygen evolution reaction in alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) solution with a given potential that the reaction is not electrochemical, as conjugate reaction at cathode could not be identified. The concentration changes in the constituents around the cathode [hydroxyl ion, hexacyanoferrate(III)], hexacyanoferrate(II) remain constant without evolving hydrogen, while around the anode there is a change in the pH, hexacyanoferrate(III and II) concentration and evolution of oxygen which is observed to be continuous. This led us to infer that in the cell, around the anode, hexacyanoferrate(III) ions and hydroxyl ions are accumulating due to electrostatic force of attraction resulting in a concentration zone, similar to the one observed in the case of solid potassium hydroxide and hexacyanoferrate(III) system. To verify this assumption experimentally, hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration changes in the two systems, viz. solid potassium hydroxide-hexacyanoferrate(III) solution and alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) solution with potential, were measured while evolving the same quantity of oxygen (about 4.5 ml). The concentration changes of hexacyanoferrate(III) in the two systems to evolve the oxygen are comparable when a correction is applied for the side reaction in the case of solid potassium hydroxide-hexacyanoferrate(III) solution and the details of the experimental results are given in Table 3.

Kinetics of reaction: With a view to assessing the individual order of the reaction with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III) and hydroxyl ion concentration, plots of their concentrations against time are drawn

and given in Figs. 4, 5 and 6. It is easy to see that the rates are first order with reference to total hexacyanoferrate(III) and hydroxyl ions. To assess

also in a side reaction, probably in the hydrolysis reaction.

The fact that the reaction is first order with reference to hydroxyl ion concentration confirms that the hydrolysis takes place in steps as shown in the above equations (9)-(12), and not in a single step as in equation (13).

Thus, it is clear from equations (9)-(12), the reaction (9) is most likely to be the rate-determining step, since the first attack of the hydroxyl is on the octahedral structure distorting the symmetry. Once the first CN^- is replaced, the further reaction proceeds fast and finally resulting in ferric hydroxide or hydrated ferric oxide.

Conclusion : It appears that there is a threshold concentration for the reaction between potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) and hydroxyl ion to take place evolving oxygen. This threshold concentration

TABLE 3—DETAILS OF EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Sl. no.	Parameter	Solid KOH-hexacyanoferrate(III)	Alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) solution with applied potential
1.	Initial concentration of ferrate(III)	3.11×10^{-3} mol/60 ml	3.22×10^{-3}
2.	Final concentration of ferrate(III)	2.93×10^{-3} mol/60 ml	3.09×10^{-3}
3.	Ferrate(III) consumed	1.73×10^{-3} mol/60 ml	1.27×10^{-3}
4.	Oxygen evolved	1.73×10^{-4} mol	1.85×10^{-4}
5.	Hexacyanoferrate(II) evolved	9.82×10^{-4} mol	8.99×10^{-4}
6.	Ratio of 4 to 3	1 : 10	1 : 6.9
7.	Ratio of 4 to 5	1 : 5.7	1 : 4.7

the overall reaction, a plot of $\log(a-x)/(b-x)$ vs time was drawn (Fig. 7), where a is the initial hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration and b is the initial hydroxyl ion concentration. The straight line confirms that the overall reaction is second order. It is, however, noted from Table 3 that for one mole of oxygen evolved, 6.9 moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) is consumed. This implies that hexacyanoferrate(III) is not only consumed for oxygen evolution but

Fig. 4. Total hexacyanoferrate(III) remaining vs time.

Fig. 5. Hexacyanoferrate(III) consumed for oxygen evolution vs time.

Fig. 6. Total OH ion concentration remaining vs time.

Fig. 7. Log $\left[\frac{a-x}{b-x} \right]$ vs time.

could be limited by applying a known potential to alkaline solutions. Efforts are presently in progress to identify the parameters that define the threshold concentration at the reaction zone.

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